

A Unified Algorithm For Robotic-Assisted Cardiac Endovascular Surgery: Supplementary Materials

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I. A DETAILED DESCRIPTION OF THE STEPS OF THE UNIFIED ALGORITHM FOR ROBOTIC-ASSISTED CARDIAC ENDOVASCULAR SURGERY

The methodology of surgery can be divided into two stages: general, which includes diagnostic and final stages typical of any cardiac endovascular surgery, and therapeutic, which differs from the chosen surgical approach. The main movements of the surgeon during an endovascular operation include grasping the tool, moving, and rotating it [1]. All stages of endovascular intervention are performed under X-ray control.

A. Puncture of the Blood Vessel

Every endovascular intervention begins with access to the vessel. The access to the vessel is performed using the Seldinger technique [2]. To the best of our knowledge, this algorithm step has not yet been implemented in any existing endovascular robots.

After this step, there are different types of intervention. The first is aimed at dilating the affected part of the vessel, including balloon angioplasty and stenting. The second is aimed at treating abnormalities in the heart's electrical activity, including endovascular ablation.

B. Insertion and Advancing of the Tools

The first step is "Insertion of the diagnostic guidewire into the catheter". Insertion of the diagnostic guidewire into the catheter takes place (Fig. 2 (a)). To the best of our knowledge, this algorithm step has not yet been implemented in any existing endovascular robots.

The catheter and the diagnostic guidewire are then inserted into the introducer – this step is called the "Insertion of the catheter into the introducer" (Fig. 2 (b)). To the best of our knowledge, this algorithm step has not yet been implemented in any existing endovascular robots.

The advancement of the tool is performed by manipulating the proximal tip of the tool (which is outside the patient's body). Pulling and pushing allows the tool to be advanced, and rotation allows the selection of the required vessel at

Fig. 1. Vascular access for percutaneous insertion of an introducer sheath using Seldinger technique [2]: (a) Vessel punctured with the needle until blood backflows. (b) A flexible j-tip guidewire advanced through the needle into the vessel lumen. (c) The needle is removed, and the wire is left in place. The hole around the wire can be enlarged with a scalpel. (d) The introducer sheath and dilator are placed over the guidewire. (e) The introducer sheath and dilator advanced over the guidewire into the vessel. (f) Dilator and guidewire removed, while the introducer sheath is left in the vessel.

Fig. 2. (a) Insertion of the diagnostic guidewire into the catheter. (b) Insertion of the catheter into the introducer. (c) Advancing the diagnostic guidewire through the artery; Advancing the catheter along the diagnostic guidewire. (d) Extraction of the diagnostic guidewire.

bifurcations, as the tool has a J-shaped tip. The diagnostic guidewire is then passed through the artery (Fig. 2 (c)). This step of the algorithm can be performed using commercial robots (Magellan, CorPath 200, CorPath GRX, R-One) [3], [4] and academic robots (CathBot, Endovascular Catheterisation Robotic System (E CRS), Robotic endovascular intervention system (REIS), Robotic System for Endovascular Surgery

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Fig. 3. Angiography: (a) Connecting the injector with a contrast agent to the catheter. (b) Injection of the contrast agent.

(ROSES), Vascular Interventional Surgery Robot (VISR), H. Rafii-Tari et al., H.-J. Cha et al., N. K. Sankaran et al., I. Naudin et al., H. Qian et al., Z. Yang et al., C. Lyu et al., S. Cao et al.) [5]–[17].

The catheter is advanced along the diagnostic guidewire to the vessel of interest (Fig. 2 (c)). It can be performed using commercial robots (Magellan, CorPath 200, CorPath GRX) and academic robots (Advanced Robotics for Magnetic Manipulation (ARMM), CathBot, ECRS, MicroVAST, REIS, ROSES, VISR, Y. Fu et al., C. J. Payne et al., H. Rafii-Tari et al., H.-J. Cha et al., N. K. Sankaran et al., I. Naudin et al., C. Lyu et al., S. Cao et al.) [5]–[8], [11]–[21].

Then, there is a step called “Extraction of the diagnostic guidewire” (Fig. 2 (d)). This step of the algorithm can be performed using commercial robots (Magellan, CorPath 200, CorPath GRX, R-One) and academic robots (CathBot, ECRS, REIS, ROSES, VISR, H. Rafii-Tari et al., H.-J. Cha et al., N. K. Sankaran et al., I. Naudin et al., H. Qian et al., Z. Yang et al., C. Lyu et al., S. Cao et al.).

C. Angiography

At the angiography step, a syringe with contrast agent is connected to the catheter, and the contrast agent is injected (Fig. reffIG: angio (a, b)). This allows the location of the lesion, assessment of the nature of thrombus formation, and determination of the optimal surgical approach. To the best of our knowledge, this algorithm step has not yet been implemented in any existing endovascular robots.

D. Insertion and Advancing of the Coronary Guidewire

After the angiography, the therapeutic stage begins. A Y-connector is connected to the catheter – this is “Connecting the Y-connector to the catheter” (Fig. 4 (a)). To the best of our knowledge, this algorithm step has not yet been implemented in any existing endovascular robots.

Then the coronary guidewire is inserted into the tip of the catheter (Fig. 4 (b)). This step of the algorithm can be performed using commercial robots (Magellan, CorPath 200, CorPath GRX, R-One) and academic robots (CathBot, ECRS, REIS, ROSES, VISR, H. Rafii-Tari et al., H.-J. Cha et al., N. K. Sankaran et al., I. Naudin et al., H. Qian et al., Z. Yang et al., C. Lyu et al., S. Cao et al.). The next step is advancing the coronary guidewire into the area of arterial stenosis (Fig. 4 (b)). It can be performed using commercial robot (R-One) and academic robots (CathBot, REIS).

Fig. 4. (a) Connecting the Y-connector to the catheter. (b) Insertion of the coronary guidewire to the tip of the catheter; Advancing the coronary guidewire into the area of arterial stenosis.

Fig. 5. Balloon angioplasty: (a) Putting the balloon catheter on the coronary guidewire; Advancing the balloon catheter to the edge of the coronary guidewire. (b) Advancing the balloon catheter along the coronary guidewire at the site of arterial stenosis (c) Inflating of the balloon. (d) Deflating of the balloon. (e) Extraction of the balloon catheter.

E. Putting on the coronary guidewire

Starting from this step, the algorithm is divided into different types of endovascular intervention (balloon angioplasty, stenting, or stenting with a self-expanding stent). Depending on the type of surgery, the catheter (the balloon catheter, the balloon catheter with a stent, the delivery systems with a self-expanding stent) is placed at the tip of the coronary guidewire (Fig. 5 (a), Fig. 6 (a), Fig. 7 (a)). To the best of our knowledge, this algorithm step has not yet been implemented in any existing endovascular robots.

F. Advancing the catheter to the edge of the coronary guidewire

Push and pull movements advance the catheter to the edge of the coronary guidewire (Fig. 5 (a), Fig. 6 (a), Fig. 7 (a)). This algorithm step can be performed using commercial robots (CorPath 200, CorPath GRX, R-One) and academic robots (CathBot, REIS).

G. Advancing along the coronary guidewire at the site of arterial stenosis

The tool (balloon catheter for balloon angioplasty, the balloon catheter with a stent for stenting, the delivery systems with a self-expanding stent for stenting with a self-expanding stent) is then advanced along the coronary guidewire at the site of arterial stenosis. The balloon is positioned at the target position so that the most stenosed segment is expanded at

Fig. 6. Stenting: (a) Putting the balloon catheter with a stent on the coronary guidewire; Advancing the balloon catheter to the edge of the coronary guidewire. (b) Advancing the balloon catheter with a stent along the coronary guidewire at the site of arterial stenosis. (c) Inflating of the balloon. (d) Deflating of the balloon. (e) Extraction of the balloon catheter with a stent.

Fig. 7. Stenting with a self-expanding stent: (a) Putting the delivery systems with a self-expanding stent on the coronary guidewire; Advancing the delivery systems with a self-expanding stent to the edge of the coronary guidewire. (b) Advancing the delivery systems with a self-expanding stent along the coronary guidewire at the site of arterial stenosis. (c) Extraction of the external catheter. (d) Extraction of the delivery system.

the expense of the central part of the balloon (Fig. 5 (b), Fig. 6 (b)). The delivery systems with a self-expanding stent is positioned in a similar method (Fig. 7 (b)). It can be performed using commercial robot (R-One) and academic robots (CathBot, REIS).

After this stage, there is a division into different types of endovascular intervention, both in terms of the type of tools used and the actions performed.

H. Inflating/Deflating of the balloon

The next step is to dilate the lesion with a balloon if balloon angioplasty or stenting is being considered. The balloon is inflated using an inflator that generates high pressure within the balloon. The plunger is compressed until the inflator registers pressure in several atmospheres. The balloon contour is visible on the fluoroscopic monitor. Inflation is performed under fluoroscopic control to ensure full balloon expansion (Fig. 5 (c), Fig. 6 (c)). After balloon angioplasty, the balloon is fully deflated (Fig. 5 (d), Fig. 6 (d)). In the case of stenting, the balloon is also placed and inflated. Only

the balloon is additionally placed with a stent, which expands when the balloon is inflated. During stenting, a balloon is placed and inflated at the site of the lesion. The balloon contains a stent, which expands when inflated and is inserted into the vessel wall after the balloon is fully deflated. To the best of our knowledge, this algorithm step has not yet been implemented in any existing endovascular robots.

I. Extraction of the balloon catheter

Balloon removal is performed the same way as insertion, using linear movements (Fig. 5 (e), Fig. 6 (e)). It can be performed using commercial robots (CorPath 200, CorPath GRX, R-One) and academic robots (CathBot, REIS). After this step, if an error occurs during the surgery (e.g., insufficient dilation of the blood vessel/no effect/difficulties associated with using endovascular tools), it is possible to go back and repeat the main step of the surgery.

J. Extraction of the external catheter and the delivery system

After positioning the delivery systems with a self-expanding stent, remove the external catheter and then extract the delivery system (Fig. 7 (c, d)). These steps of the algorithm can be performed using REIS.

K. Angiography

The process of repeat angiography is similar to that described in Section I-C. Repeat angiography can be used to evaluate the success of the procedure. Suppose an error occurs during the surgery (e.g., insufficient dilation of the blood vessel/no effect/difficulties associated with using endovascular tools). In that case, it is possible to go back and repeat the main step of the surgery.

L. Extraction of the Tools

If the operation is successful, the steps of extracting the tools (coronary guidewire, catheter, and introducer) begin. The first step is called “Extraction of the coronary guidewire” and can be performed using commercial robots (Magellan, CorPath 200, CorPath GRX, R-One) and academic robots (CathBot, ECRS, REIS, ROSES, VISR, H. Rafii-Tari et al., H.-J. Cha et al., N. K. Sankaran et al., I. Naudin et al., H. Qian et al., Z. Yang et al., C. Lyu et al., S. Cao et al.).

The second step is called “Extraction of the catheter” and can be performed using commercial robots (Magellan, CorPath 200, CorPath GRX) and academic robots (ARMM, CathBot, ECRS, MicroVAST, REIS, ROSES, VISR, Y. Fu et al., C. J. Payne et al., H. Rafii-Tari et al., H.-J. Cha et al., N. K. Sankaran et al., I. Naudin et al., C. Lyu et al., S. Cao et al.).

The third step is called “Extraction of the introducer” (Fig. 8). To the best of our knowledge, this algorithm step has not yet been implemented in any existing endovascular robots.

Fig. 8. (a) A vessel after balloon angioplasty. (b) A vessel after stenting. (c) A vessel after stenting with a self-expanding stent.

Fig. 9. Endovascular ablation: (a) Insertion of the ablation catheter. (b) Advancing the ablation catheter to the point of interest. (c) Ablation.

M. Insertion and Advancing of the Ablation Catheter

The first step is the insertion of the electrophysiological catheter into the vessel through the introducer. This step is called “Insertion of the ablation catheter” (Fig. 9 (a)).

The catheter is then advanced through the vessels in the heart to the lesion. The advancement of the tool is performed by the surgeon manipulating the proximal tip of the tool (which is outside the patient’s body). Pulling and pushing allows the tool to be advanced (Fig. 9 (b)).

These algorithm steps can be performed using commercial robots (CGCI, Amigo RCS, Genesis RMN, Niobe, Sensei X) [4].

N. Ablation

The tip of the electrophysiology catheter is placed at the target site in the heart, and the affected area is ablated (Fig. 9 (c)) to perform this step. The ablation procedure mainly uses electrical energy to destroy cells with abnormal electrical activity through thermal heating [22]. This step of the algorithm can be performed using commercial robots (CGCI, Amigo RCS, Genesis RMN, Niobe, Sensei X).

O. Extraction of the ablation catheter

The tool is extracted in the same way as it is inserted. This algorithm step can be performed using commercial robots (CGCI, Amigo RCS, Genesis RMN, Niobe, Sensei X).

P. Compression of the puncture site

The final stage of endovascular intervention is compression of the puncture site. To the best of our knowledge, this algorithm step has not yet been implemented in any existing endovascular robots.

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